

MARKETING STRATEGIES IN AGRICULTURE**Urazova Klara Kalbaevna****The Republic of Karakalpakstan****English teacher at school 26 in Kungrad region**

Annotation: Marketers create strategic, tactical, and operational plans for agricultural enterprises and companies' production and sales activities, which include forecasts of target market development, the agricultural sector and the company's objective, strategy and tactics of action in it, the company's brand, price, and sales policy, as well as promotion and promotion. This article examines agricultural marketing techniques, including ideas and considerations.

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The effectiveness of entrepreneurship in the village will be determined by the establishment of an alternative strategy. According to the state and amount of demand, market coverage, market share, brand, and market innovation, marketing offers a variety of worldwide and universal market tactics. Marketing programs play a considerably larger part in marketing operations, and the function of an agricultural farmer in the market is in some ways dependent on the quality of these programs' development and implementation.

Commodity policy is a form of marketing program that is part of the marketing mix complex and tries to strengthen the competitive position of agricultural farmers. This approach, according to the statement, will be focused on increasing the consumer features of agricultural products already being produced, the invention and competitiveness of new types, and the optimization of agricultural product life cycles and assortment. These techniques attempt to elevate agricultural product quality classifications and features from a given market segment to the level of specific consumer requirements, assuring effective sales. Pricing policy refers to the determination of an agriculture farmer's and his or her

company's price strategy in long-term market movement as well as short-term price tactics in relation to each group and type of agricultural products as well as a specific market segment. Price policy allows for the adjustment of a commodity's price, the enhancement of its competitiveness (as required to conduct trade activities under market conditions), and the establishment of a price based on market requirements and other considerations.

The construction of direct and indirect sales channels for agricultural products is part of the sale policy. The direct technique demonstrates that the manufacturer's Agriculture Department and the company's economics, that is, through its own sales system, establish sales branches, warehouses, stations, and technical service centers directly. The word "indirect method" refers to commerce that takes place through third-party intermediaries. The agricultural farmer's sales policy also includes the development of retail, cost-effective, and international trade sales systems. The planning and implementation of activities aimed at introducing agricultural products to the market is referred to as communication policy. Various forms of advertising are utilized in this field, as well as public relations, sales promotion, pre- and post-sales service, and the usage of modern trademarks, or "brands." Marketing is a comprehensive picture of a company's agricultural management activities and its management activities, characterized by general principles and functions, and an agricultural farmer's organization of production and sales is aimed at satisfying customer expectations. However, depending on the nature and aspect of agricultural farmer management using the marketing concept, different views of marketing are shown.

1. There are several methods of marketing for agricultural products, depending on the features of the demand:
2. Convert negative, negative demand into positive demand.
3. When there is no demand for a certain commodity in the market at a given time, creative demand is created.
4. Incentive-based demand increases at a lower level;
5. Increase your attenuation demand through remarketing;

6. Demand for variable trigger is stabilized through marketing;
7. Marketing clearly lowers high demand; – supportive-ensures optimal demand retention.

Depending on the look of the goods and services given, marketing is split into many sorts. Consumer goods marketing, agricultural products marketing, banking and financial marketing, Trade Marketing, tourist business marketing, scientific and technical marketing, idea marketing, and other sorts of marketing exist, each with their own distinct qualities. There are several types of agricultural marketing, depending on the type of organization and agriculture farmer and company, as well as the nature of the business activities: non-profit and commercial marketing, agricultural small business marketing, election marketing, individual person marketing, and so on.

Marketing is a scientifically developed approach for analyzing and forecasting consumer demand. Marketing is the capacity to look at a firm through the eyes of a customer from the other side of the counter. This refers to your capacity to find and keep a buyer, as well as supply him with better and faster service than your competition and meet his needs. If the company first conducted production research, the marketing system will concentrate its efforts on analyzing the market situation. If the selection of agricultural products is planned solely for the purpose of enhancing quality, then the marketing system primarily considers the needs of the consumer.

Marketers develop strategic, tactical, and operational plans for their agricultural enterprises' and companies' production and sales activities, which include the purpose, strategy, and tactics of the target and the company to act on it, as well as the brand, price, and sales policy, as well as the policy of promoting the sale and conducting promotional activities. The effectiveness of rural areas will be determined by the establishment of an alternate strategy. According to the state and amount of demand, market coverage, market share, brand, and market innovation, marketing offers a variety of worldwide and universal market tactics. Marketing programs occupy a much more important place in

marketing activities, in some sense the role of the agricultural farmer in the market depends on the quality development and effective implementation of these programs.

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